

INTRODUCING THE CONCEPT OF DIPLOMATIC LANGUAGE TO IR MASTER'S STUDENTS

Babayan A.

*PhD in Philology, Associate Professor
Yerevan State University, Faculty of International Relations,
Department of Diplomatic Service and Communication, Armenia
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8630-2779>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14008561>*

Abstract

This study emphasizes the significance of a comprehensive understanding of the concept of diplomatic language among Master's students in International Relations, positioning it within a theoretical systemic framework as a core component of their professional toolkit. Through an extensive review and synthesis of the existing literature, the paper aims to provide a holistic perspective of the concept of diplomatic language by exploring its various cognitive aspects and practical applications. It delves into its key features such as politeness and tact, as well as the cultural nuances as integral components of diplomatic discourse. The paper examines diplomatic language within a historical context tracing its evolution, and underscores the diplomat's strategic choice of the language as a defining feature. The study also highlights the importance of the continuous creation and generation of new diplomatic terms and notions, reflecting the evolving nature of the field. The study suggests that a deeper grasp of the concept of the diplomatic language will enhance students' linguistic competence, empowering them to employ diplomatic language effectively and successfully in their future professional endeavors.

Keywords: concept components; holistic perspectives; international relations; language choice; new terms

Introduction

A course entitled 'Aspects of Diplomatic Language' is taken at the Master's programme of the Faculty of International Relations at YSU. Designed for 6 credits, the correlation of its theoretical and practical parts is 75% to 25%.

The course aims at acquainting students with the key notions as well as main techniques of application of diplomatic language, thus enabling them to grasp various expressions of its characteristics and peculiarities. It works on building up their competence and faculty/ability/capability of successful application of diplomatic language in their future professional life.

The general knowledge and special vocabulary that students gain at the Bachelor's programme form a good basis for their further theoretical deliberations/considerations. Still, a theoretical systemic approach to the nature / constitution and use of the language of their profession opens up wider horizons for future IR specialists.

Any theoretical discourse of a concrete topic starts with defining the boundaries, classifying and clarifying the concepts that play the central role. This is why we start the introduction of the course with the discussion of the concept of diplomatic language. For, as Demosthenes puts it: 'Ambassadors have no control over ships or places or soldiers or citadels - no one puts such things in their hands - but over words and times' (Demosthenes, 2009: §167).

Diplomatic language has been extensively discussed in the academic fora. It has been comprehensively studied in articles published as separate collections (*Language and Diplomacy*, 2001; *English for Diplomatic Purposes*, 2016; *Diplomatic and Political Interpreting Explained*,

2022, etc.), in chapters of books on diplomacy (H. Nicolson, *Diplomacy*, 1939, chap. X; E. Satow, *A*

Guide to Diplomatic Practice, 2011, chap. VII), in different academic journals. Each article focuses on an aspect or some aspects of the diplomatic language, thus, layer by layer adding to the completeness of the picture of the concept and notion and practical implementation kit of the diplomatic language.

Still in the first half of the XX century Sir E. Satow and Sir H. Nicolson in their books on diplomacy presented diplomatic language as an integral component of the diplomatic practice, described its evolution through time, and defined certain aspects of it, emphasizing the importance of precision and truthfulness in diplomatic communication, while acknowledging the role of diplomatic ambiguity or understatement when necessary to maintain flexibility and avoid conflicts (Nicolson, 1939; Satow, 1917/2011).

The tradition has been carried on by scholars and diplomats who continue to study and discuss the interrelation between language and diplomacy (A. Matteucci, K. Jaber, S. Nick, P. Harvey), language and diplomatic negotiations (T. Jacobs, D. Ford & P. Luksetich, R. Cohen), and the use of linguistic techniques such as ambiguity, historical rhetoric and political speechmaking in diplomacy (D. Pehar, N. Scott, S. Pokhrel). Others have focused on the correlation between diplomatic language and cross-cultural issues (A. Kirkpatrick et al., M. LaBaron & V. Pillay, B. Scott), diplomatic correspondence (L. Blinkova, D. Kappeler, K. Hamilton), the coherence of interpretation and diplomacy (V. Cremona & H. Mallia, M. Kadric et al.), and the role of information technologies in diplomacy (J. Kurbalija, B. Scott), among many other topics.

The vast array of aspects and nuances surrounding the diplomatic language presents both challenges and opportunities when designing the course framework and content for the Master's program. It highlights the importance of establishing key concepts throughout the course, for

‘concepts are the building blocks of thought (*Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*, 2024). The concept of diplomatic language, in particular, serves as the fundamental building block that logically sets the foundation for the course.

Research questions and methodological pathway This study poses the following research questions:

- a) To identify the core notions and the mental representations that the concept of diplomatic language encompasses.
- b) To create ‘shortcuts’ – methods for easier perception and reproduction of the facets and components of the concept of diplomatic language for students’ further application.

The study employs a theoretical approach, with a methodology centered on a comprehensive review and synthesis of existing literature. It draws on various theoretical frameworks relevant to the topic. The primary methods involve an extensive literature review, including relevant academic journals, books and conference papers.

This research is grounded on the insights of distinguished authors within the fields of critical discourse analysis, cognitive linguistics, and sociolinguistic research. It aims to combine the perspectives of both scholars and career diplomats to provide a holistic understanding of the concept of diplomatic language.

By synthesizing these materials and adapting them to the course design, the article aims to facilitate the Master’s students’ comprehension of the concept of diplomatic language. This will help them better understand the theoretical literature they encounter daily, and promote more accurate and precise use of diplomatic language in practice.

Starting from the basics

Any introduction to the concept of diplomatic language begins with an interpretation of what diplomacy is, serving as a launching pad to explain why a specific type of language with distinct characteristics is used in this field, and what its implementation entails. A brief reference to how various scholars, diplomats and statesmen define diplomacy can offer valuable insights for further consideration.

The *Dictionary of Diplomacy* defines diplomacy as ‘the conduct of relations between sovereign states through the medium of officials based at home or abroad’ (G. Berridge and A. James, 2003: 70). However, this neutral definition does not particularly aid our purpose. *Britannica* defines diplomacy as ‘an estab-

lished method of influencing the decisions and behavior of foreign governments and peoples through dialogue, negotiation and other measures short of war or violence’ (*Encyclopedia Britannica*, 2024). This interpretation provides a more actionable understanding. Meanwhile, H. Kissinger describes diplomacy as ‘the art of relating states to each other by agreement rather than by the exercise of force’ (Kissinger, 2020). This brings us closer to understanding the type of language used in diplomacy.

S. Pokhrel’s defines diplomacy as ‘mediation carried out between two different entities, implying the application of tactics and intelligence to further the conduct of official relations that are mutually beneficial’ (Pokhrel, 2022: 390). This definition closely aligns with that of Sir Ernest Satow, a distinguished diplomat and scholar, who considers diplomacy as ‘the application of intelligence and tact to the conduct of official relations between governments’ (Satow, 2011: 52).

All these definitions, and many others, emphasize the key role of diplomacy: to communicate and influence the outside world for the benefit of one’s country, using tact, intelligence and methods short of war. As W. Churchill famously said, ‘Meeting jaw to jaw is better than war.’ (Churchill, 1954).

Diplomatic processes – such as communicating, negotiating, reaching and formulating agreements, and collecting, creating, transmitting and recording knowledge – all rely on language that is both ‘intelligent and tactful’ (Satow, 2011: 67), ‘pleasing to the listener, without disturbing words, yet precise and useful’ (Bhagavad Gita: ch.7).

However, politeness and tact, as well as carefully phrased utterances are essential components of everyday communication, often referred to as ‘diplomatic language’. Such type of language aims to help the speaker achieve their goal without causing discomfort or harm to the interlocutor. Such diplomatic language is common in all areas of life, from household conversations to business negotiations, both in personal and professional context. English, in particular, is sensitive to the use of diplomatic language socially, with ‘Diplomatic English’ described as a way to be strong without making people angry’ (Jong-Pauley, 2021).

The situations when diplomatic language is appropriate are grouped as (a) giving bad news, (b) making requests, (c) giving commands, (d) making objections, (e) negotiating, (f) making suggestions, or (g) blaming someone (Streat, 2016).

To illustrate the above said a few examples would suffice.

Non-considerate language	Diplomatic language
(a) This report is awful.	This report is not really up to the standard.
(b) Come here.	Could you come here!
(c) That’s a bad idea.	I’m not sure that’s a good idea.

The diplomatic English that is used socially and widely on a daily basis also forms an essential part of

formal diplomatic communication – the language of diplomacy itself. Therefore, equipping students with these technique is highly relevant. In this article we

have selected several of the most common techniques that smoothly infuse the speaker's language with tact and politeness. These techniques are as follows:

1. The use of hedges, also called softeners. These words or phrases usually come at the beginning of the sentence, lessen the impact of the sentence or give it a shade of softness and uncertainty. E.g. 'I wonder', 'Unfortunately', 'I'm afraid,' 'Actually,' 'To be honest', 'I'm sorry, but...', 'With respect ...', 'There seems to be...', etc. (E.g. 'There seems to be a problem with the incoming mail'; 'I'm afraid, we have to cancel the talks'.)

2. The use of qualifiers/modifiers to minimize the certainty and assertiveness of a statement:

a little, a bit, slightly, a little bit, very + adjective, etc. (E.g. 'The delegation is going to be a little late'; 'We face a bit of a problem/one or two problems'.)

3. The use of modal verbs *would, could, may, might*. (E.g. 'We could do with more time'; It would be so helpful to start the negotiations a bit earlier'.)

4. Rephrasing negative sentences or negative adjectives so that they sound more positive. For example, *can't* and *won't* sound quite negative. But if *be able to* or *in the position of* are used, the sentence sounds diplomatic. E.g. 'We won't be able to sign this document. / We are not in the position of signing this document.'

5. When negative adjectives are replaced by *not+very+positive adjective*, the utterance sounds more persuasive, though without a negative impact. E.g. 'Their proposals are weak.' is replaced with 'Their proposals are not very strong.', or 'The reception was awful.' – 'The reception was not very friendly'.

6. To make the utterances more polite, the Present Simple tense is often changed into Past Simple, or to Progressive tenses. The meaning of the sentence is still in the present, but the change of the tense-form of the verb adds softness to the say. E.g. 'Do you have time to meet tomorrow to discuss this?' (Present Simple) is replaced by 'I wondered if you have time to meet tomorrow' (Past Simple), or 'I am/was wondering if you have time to meet tomorrow' (Present/Past Progressive).

7. Phrasing questions negatively is another helpful technique that imparts tact and politeness. E.g. 'Wouldn't it be better to start now?' 'Shouldn't we wait for our allies?' etc.

8. Similarly, to show appreciation and thank for cooperation and positive outcome of a deal, the English use different ways of saying 'Thank you', like 'I appreciate...', 'I am grateful for ...', 'We could not have done this without you', etc.

The list of the linguistic tools and techniques that transform a simple statement into a diplomatic one is much more extensive than what has been discussed above. However, highlighting the overlap and interconnection between the diplomatic English used in everyday socializing and the formal language of diplomacy, while building awareness of the most common techniques, best serves our objective. Now that students can clearly identify the dual use of the term 'diplomatic English', a smooth transition to the discussion of the broader concept of diplomatic language is established.

Coherence of meanings

To gain a fuller understanding of the concept of diplomatic language, students should distinguish between three distinctive meanings of the term.

In its first sense, 'diplomatic language' refers to the actual languages, such as French, English or others employed by diplomats in communication, whether in correspondence or negotiation.

In the second sense, it denotes the set of phrases that have, over the centuries, become part of the standard diplomatic vocabulary, including terms like *modus vivendi, veto, cold war, and pacta sunt servanda*.

In the third and most common sense, it describes the selected form of language that allows diplomats to convey complex or potentially controversial ideas without being offensive or impolite (Nicolson, 1939).

A brief review of these meanings will provide a general idea of the range of notions and interpretations encompassed by this concept.

Historically the actual language used by diplomats has varied over the centuries. The first known diplomatic treaty, concluded around 2450 BC between the city-state of Elba and Kingdom of Hamazi was written in Sumerian-Akkadian. This treaty is the most ancient preserved document, inscribed in cuneiform on a clay tablet dating back to the early Bronze Age. (The History Files, 2024) Other languages have since followed suit.

As a rule, in the classic Ancient World - much like today - the lingua franca was that of the dominant power, first Greek and then Latin. As Latin became the primary language of the church, the court, science and law, its longevity as the language of diplomacy extended well into the middle of the 18th century, when French took up the mantle.

However, the new realities of the 20th century, including the conclusion of World War I, the Paris Peace Conference of January 1919, and the emergence of democratic diplomacy – distinct from that conducted by sovereigns – made it increasingly impractical to rely solely on French in diplomatic practice. Peace Treaty of Versailles concluded in June 1919 stipulated the following: 'The Present Treaty, of which the French and English texts are both authentic, shall be ratified' (Peace Treaty of Versailles, Article 440). The Treaty of Versailles signed by multiple countries was written both in French and English.

The process of English's growing dominance as a new lingua franca, accelerated especially after World War II, with the establishment of the United Nations, where English-speaking nations played a prominent role. Despite the popularity of English, French continues to play an integral role in international relations. Alongside many French-speaking countries, French is frequently used in diplomatic documents and correspondence.

In tracing the evolution of diplomatic language, students should recognize that, limited to certain geographic areas and political groups of countries at various point in history, the common diplomatic languages have included Akkadian (Assyrian Babylonian), Literary Chinese in the East, Greek, Latin, Arabic, Spanish, Portuguese, Russian, Italian, Dutch, German, French and English. Currently, the official working languages

at the United Nations are English, French, Russian, Chinese, Spanish and Arabic.

With this abundance of diplomatic languages, along with the native language(s) of the interlocutor(s), a central question arises: what language should a diplomat choose for communication.

The diplomat's choice

The choice of communication language of is another critical aspect of the concept of diplomatic language. Selecting a particular language serves as a clear demonstration of the intention to be diplomatic and to achieve benefits without revealing underlying motives.

Moreover, even when all the participants can communicate in a common language, significant differences in the perception and interpretation of that same common language can arise from country to country, from culture to culture.

Diplomats have several strategies in their toolkit to address this issue, depending on the occasion, purpose and medium of communication, as any chosen solution may have both positive and negative consequences.

One possible solution is for one interlocutor to speak the language of the other. However, unless their proficiency in that language is perfect – which is rare – they may find themselves at a disadvantage when facing a native speaker. The other party may gain significant advantage, including possible political implications.

The second option is for both sides to use a third, neutral language. However, this approach can hide potential problems. If neither side possesses complete linguistic proficiency, serious misunderstandings may arise.

The third option, commonly used, involves the presence of interpreters, especially in multilateral diplomacy or high-level negotiations, as politicians and statesmen often do not speak foreign languages. However, this method also has its disadvantages: it can be time-consuming, costly, and occasionally inaccurate.

So, which language should a well-trained and experienced diplomat, who speaks several languages fluently, choose to use in a given situation? The choice of language in diplomacy can have significant implications. The first logical answer might be 'the language he speaks best'. However, professionally speaking, it is not always the wisest choice.

Sometimes it may be more prudent to use a language in which one is less proficient for several reasons: (1) to avoid using the native tongue of the interlocutor and thereby placing them on a more equitable footing; (2) to avoid a language that may carry undesirable political connotations (e.g., speaking Hebrew to an Arab); (3) to make a gesture of goodwill or courtesy; (4) as a sign of special respect towards the conversation partner or their country.

Thus, the choice and proper application of diplomatic language help to build relationships, secure agreements, adhere to public courtesy norms, and facilitate the understanding of unspoken cues, while decoding the linguistic signals that the other side may be sending.

Diplomatic language as action

Another facet of the concept of diplomatic language is its function as a tool for action. It is a truism that language is the primary tool for diplomats serving as a means of information gathering and a form of communication. Beyond this, language also serves as a powerful device for action.

The Speech Act theory developed by J. L. Austin and J. Searle, and others addresses this critical feature of language, particularly in its application within diplomacy. The theory posits that words not only have the power to bring about actions – evident in many famous speeches by prominent politicians and diplomats – but that by saying or in saying something we are doing something, many utterances are a form of action in themselves (Austin, 1962: 14). This occurs when we warn, promise, suggest, agree, advise, and engage in similar communicative acts. In these sentences we *are doing something* rather than saying something.

In his interpretation of speech acts Austin distinguishes three main types of speech acts that occur when someone speaks:

- a) Locutionary act – the act of saying
- b) Illocutionary act – the act of saying something as asserting, complaining, apologizing, commanding, requesting, etc. The strong intent is present.
- c) Perlocutionary act – one that results in an actual effect of the listener (Austin, 1962: 12).

Out of these, the illocutionary type of speech is the main acting component in the diplomat's language as action.

According to John Searle, there are only five illocutionary points speakers achieve or propositions in an utterance, that make their intent clear. They are:

1. the assertive/representative point, when they represent how things are in the world;
2. the commissive point, when they commit themselves to doing something;
3. the directive point when they make an attempt to get hearers to do something;
4. the declaratory point, when they do things in the world at the moment of this utterance solely by virtue of saying that they do. E.g. 'We shall not participate in this war';
5. the expressive point, when they express their attitudes about objects and facts of the world (Searle, 1976: 16).

All these aspects are inherently present in diplomatic speech, transforming a diplomat's words into action. By employing assertive, commissive, directive, declaratory and expressive elements of language in their speeches, negotiations, statements and notes, diplomats actively engage with the world through language, using it not only as a tool, but, actually, as an end in itself.

Thus, the capacity of diplomatic language to serve as a form of action constitutes another intrinsic feature of this concept.

The cultural dimension

In highlighting the importance of one of the components of the concept of the diplomatic language as a form of action, we must acknowledge the cultural nuances that each expression of diplomatic language carries.

As noted earlier, diplomatic communication aims to avoid aggressive, insensitive, offensive and destructive language. In pursuit of its primary objectives, diplomatic communication promotes peace-making, peace-building, and peace-promoting language. Diplomats carefully choose polite and thoughtfully constructed utterances to ensure effective communication, always mindful that 'all communication is cultural' (LeBaron, 2003). Respecting other cultures and their established values, is essential for fostering cordial relationships in diplomatic discourse, especially when influenced by religiously generated norms.

Despite claims by some diplomats and scholars that the language of diplomacy should be neutral rather than culturally bound, the ideal of a neutral diplomatic language is often disconnected from the realities of ongoing diplomatic encounters on the international stage. It remains more of a wishful thinking than a practical approach.

Regardless of the insistence on so-called neutral diplomatic language, language inherently reflects cultural diversities. The same phrasing or term within diplomatic language can be perceived and interpreted differently by diplomats with diverse cultural background, as one phenomenon may have slightly varying or even completely opposing interpretations. Thus, student should be aware that the cultural nuances inherent in the concept of diplomatic language are always present.

The foreign language effect

Another important phenomenon to discuss is the so-called 'foreign language effect,' as described in 2012 paper by Boaz Keysar and his colleagues. According to their research, using a first language – one's mother tongue – can invoke irrational, emotional connections that influence decision-making. In contrast, these emotional connections tend to diminish when communicating in a foreign language. The absence of subconscious emotional undertones reduces biases and alleviates the fear of miscommunication.

The authors state: 'Using a foreign language reduces loss aversion increasing the acceptance of both hypothetical and real bets with positive expected value. We propose that these effects arise because a foreign language provides greater cognitive and emotional distance than a mother tongue.' (Keysar, 2012: 662)

An excellent example of this phenomenon is Nelson Mandela, whose native tongue was Xhosa. A remarkable negotiator, Mandela learned to use Afrikaans during his imprisonment. Whether by intuition or practice, Mandela understood the implications of this phenomenon and skillfully employed Afrikaans to his advantage. The approach has also been successfully utilized by other diplomats and politicians. Thus, the phenomenon of the 'foreign language effect' enriches our understanding of the concept of diplomatic language, particularly regarding its implementation strategies.

Term creation

Our final consideration pertains to a seemingly minor but significantly impactful phenomenon – the creation of diplomatic terms. These terms eventually become integral to the evolving diplomatic language and

become ingrained in its overall concept. This idea resonates with Nicolson's definition of diplomatic language in its second sense – 'a set of words and phrases which over the course of centuries have become a part of the ordinary diplomatic vocabulary' (Nicolson, 1939: 227).

The creation of new terms is regarded as a prerogative of diplomats, who strive to find better expressions to reflect the changing realities of international life. Drazen Pehar asserts that 'diplomats must be aware that they have the freedom not only to choose but also to make a brand new language of their own liking' (Pehar, 2001: 69). He emphasizes that 'every diplomat should try to create a better and more expressive kind of Diplomatese, because to create new terms is to create new realities' (Ibid., p. 70).

A recent example of this phenomenon is the introduction of the term 'war on terrorism' by the Bush administration, which significantly influenced US foreign policy of post - 9/11. Initially, 'terrorism' referred to violence by individuals or groups against civilians, excluding state actions. However, in this new context, it acquired a broader and more devastating meaning, implying state-sponsored military actions against large population or entire countries. The term 'war' in this phrase extended beyond a purely military effort; it suggested an expansive struggle akin to a battlefield campaign.

The phrase gained traction globally, prompting other governments to adopt it to lend moral authority to their own conflicts. For instance, Russia termed its actions in Chechnya a 'war on terrorism', as did India in Kashmir, Israel in Palestine and others. In summary, we can conclude that term creation is a vital component of a holistic understanding of the concept of diplomatic language.

Final considerations

The current study emphasizes the importance of cultivating a holistic perspective on the concept of diplomatic language for Master's students, who are preparing for careers that demand advanced communication skills. The findings indicate that diplomatic language should be viewed as a synergy of sociocultural and diplomatic elements that interact in intricate ways. These components form a cohesive whole that is crucial for a profound and meaningful understanding of the subject.

Students are encouraged to explore how these elements interconnect and influence one another across various contexts. This deeper comprehension enhances their ability to apply linguistic skills effectively in real-world scenarios, where diplomacy requires not only language proficiency but also keen awareness of its underlying sociocultural dimensions. Ultimately, this approach provides students with a competitive edge in their professional fields.

References:

1. Abu Jaber, K. (2001). *Language and Diplomacy*, Language and Diplomacy, pp. 22-25. [Electronic resource]. Available at: https://www.ati.usacademy.org/Books/Language_and_Diplomacy

2. Austin, J. (1962). *How to Do Things with Words*, Harvard University Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts, p. 12.
3. Berridge, G. and James, A. (2003). *A Dictionary of Diplomacy*, Palgrave Macmillan, 2nd edition, p. 70.
4. Churchill, W. (1954). From the *Speech in Washington D.C.* Winston Churchill Quotes. Available at: https://www.brainyquote.com/authors/winston-churchill-quotes_2
5. Cohen, R. (2001). *Language and Negotiations: A Middle East Lexicon*, Language and Diplomacy, pp. 33-46.
6. Cremona, V. A. & Mallia, H. (2001). *Interpretation and Diplomacy*, Language and Diplomacy, pp. 159-161.
7. Demosthenes, (1912). *The Public Orations of Demosthenes: Speech at the Trial of Aeschines*, Clarendon Press, Princeton, vol. 1, § 167.
8. *Encyclopaedia Britannica*, 2024. Available at: <https://www.britannica.com>
9. Ford, D. & Luksetich, P. (2016). *Negotiating in English.* / English for Diplomatic Purposes, Multilingual Matters, Bristol; Buffalo, pp. 109-148.
10. Friedrich, P. (Ed.), (2016). *English for Diplomatic Purposes*, Multilingual Matters, Bristol; Buffalo.
11. Hamilton, K. (2001). *Documenting Diplomacy: Evaluation and Documents: The Case of CSCE*, Language and Diplomacy, pp. 110-118
12. Harvey, P. (2011). *Diplomacy and the English Language*, Available at: <https://www.diplotaxis.com/ingles/>
13. Jacobs, T. (2016). *The Language Diplomats speak: A Discourse-Theoretical Approach to the Negotiations in the EURONEST Parliamentary Assembly*, College of Europe, EU Diplomacy Papers, vol. 5.
14. Jong-Pauley, B. (2021). *Diplomatic English for Business*, English Center, Amsterdam. Available at: <https://www.englishcenter.nl/>
15. Kadric, M., Rennet, S. and Schaffner R. (2022). *Diplomatic and Political Interpreting Explained*, Routledge, London.
16. Kappeler, D. (2001). *Texts in Diplomacy*, Language and Diplomacy, pp. 107-109.
17. Keysar, B., Hayakawa, S. and Sun Gyu An (2012). "The Foreign Language Effect: Thinking in a Foreign Tongue Reduces Decision Biases", *Psychological Science*, vol. 23, issue 6, pp. 661-668.
18. Kirkpatrick, A., Subhan, S. and Walkinshaw, I. (2016). *English as Lingua Franca in East and South-East Asia: Implications for Diplomatic and Intercultural Communication* / English for Diplomatic Purposes, Multilingual Matters, Bristol; Buffalo, pp. 75-93.
19. Kissinger, H. (2013). *A World Restored: Metternich, Castlereagh and the Problems of Peace*, Echo Point Books & Media. LCC.
20. Krishna in *Bhagavad Gita*. Available at: <https://www.goodreads.com/>
21. Kurbalija, J. (2001). *Hypertext in Diplomacy*, Language and Diplomacy, pp. 162-182.
22. LeBaron, M. (July, 2003). *Cross-Cultural Communication, Beyond Intractability Conflict Information Consortium*, University of Colorado, Boulder. Available at: https://www.beyondintractability.org/essay/cross-cultural_communication
23. LeBaron, M. and Pillay, V. (2006). *Conflict Across Cultures: A Unique Experience of Bridging Differences*, Nicholas Brealey Publishing, London.
24. Mateucci, A. (2001). *Language and Diplomacy – A Practitioner's View*. Language and Diplomacy, pp. 26-32.
25. Nick, S. (2001). *Use of Language in Diplomacy*, Language and Diplomacy, pp. 187-21.
26. Nicolson, H. (1939). *Diplomacy*, Oxford University Press, London, pp. 226-227. Available at: <https://archive.org/details/in.ernet.dli.2015.14552>
27. Pehar, D. (2001). *Historical Rhetoric and Diplomacy*, Language and Diplomacy, pp. 60-71.
28. Pokhrel, S. (2022). A Comparative Study on the Use of First-Person Pronouns in Ten International Diplomatic Speeches, *Journal of Research and Innovation in Language*, vol. 4, #3, pp. 290-308.
29. Satow, E. (2011). *A Guide to Diplomatic Practice*, Cambridge University Press, vol. 1, pp. 52-61. First published in 1917. Available at: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/books/guideto-diplomatic-practice/CE8BCA8ECE89A4F5D89191AA7FC5B0B8>
30. Scott, B. (2016). *Force and Grace*, English for Diplomatic Purposes, Multilingual Matters, Bristol; Buffalo, pp. 149-172.
31. Scott, N. (2001). *Ambiguity Versus Precision: The Changing Role of Terminology in Conference Diplomacy*, Language and Diplomacy, pp. 81-86.
32. Searle, J. (1976). *A Classification of Illocutionary Acts*, Language in Society, vol. 5, # 1, Cambridge University Press, pp. 16-18.
33. *Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*. (2024). Stanford University, Available at: <https://www.plato.stanford.edu>
34. Streat, S. (2016). How to use Diplomatic English in Your Next Business Meeting in English, English with a Twist, Nov. 24. Available at: <https://englishwithatwist.com/2016/11/24/>
35. Блинкова, Л. (2012) *Деловая и дипломатическая переписка на иностранном языке*, БГУ, Минск.